

Gavin Menzies and the Chinese expedition to Italy in 1434

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To the memory of Gavin Menzies (1937-2020) for perseverance in continuing the project on China's global reach and cultural influence.

A Chinese fleet in Italy

Gavin Menzies' book *1434 The Year a Chinese Fleet Arrived in Italy and Initiated the Renaissance* follows up on *1421: The Year China Discovered the World*, focusing now on China's relations with Europe through Italy. It is based on the last voyage led by Admiral Zheng He (1371-1433), also known as Ma Sanbao, as ambassador to Pope Eugene IV (1383-1447), who served as Supreme Pontiff from 1431 to 1447.

The PDF version of the Spanish text prepared by Patricio Barros, with the collaboration of Sergio Barros (2008),¹ is characterized by a wording very close to the grammar and syntax of the English language, so it would be of great interest a critical edition in Spanish language that includes a total revision of the text, such as the proper use of wording and syntax, the correct use of punctuation marks and in certain cases of spelling. This would allow comparison with the English version (*1434 The Year a Magnificent Chinese Fleet Sailed to Italy and Ignited the Renaissance*, also available in PDF). Overall, the initial translation is valid in that it assumes the author's colloquial sense to pleasantly lead the reader through a highly complex and controversial subject, where the research methods employed are combined with evidence that makes it possible to move from the strictly hypothetical to the demonstrative. Menzies emphasizes research as a process, as a pleasant colloquial discourse and does not limit himself to the cold exposition of facts, results, and evidence, but combines the demonstration with very diverse experiences in the places where clues and findings have appeared. This also represents a sledgehammer blow against boring history texts and their respective authors. A complementary part of both the new evidence and other texts on the subject can be found on the website dedicated to the book.²

A body of footnotes [in square brackets] should also be included to distinguish them from the large number of references used by the author, on various aspects that he takes for granted, biographical data on figures related to the present subject, ethnic groups, symbolic details, clearable inaccuracies, disagreements, and other questions to facilitate interpretation. Also, unlike the Spanish version, footnotes should be included, since for any regular reader, when footnotes are placed at the end of each chapter or at the end of the work, they are almost never read or overlooked.

¹ Open access on the Website at www.librosmaravillosos.com

² See <https://www.gavinmenzies.net/china/1434-2/>

Menzies approaches with new sources and very diverse contributors, the role exercised by the Chinese expedition's visit to Venice and Florence in 1434, and its subsequent influence on the development and expansion of the European Renaissance. Thus, the author considers that:

The Renaissance has traditionally been explained as a return to the classical civilizations of Greece and Rome. It seems to me that the time has come to make another assessment of this Eurocentric historical perspective. While the ideals of Greece and Rome played an important role in the Renaissance, I would suggest that the transfer of intellectual capital from China to Europe was the spark that ignited this historical and artistic stage.³

Another motivating factor is the study by Tai Peng Wang, a Canadian scholar of Chinese origin, who was acquainted with Chinese and Italian chronicles of visits by Chinese delegations to Italy during the reigns of Emperors Zhu Di (1403-1424) and Xuande (1426-1435), which also represents a forceful response to the barrage of criticism, suspicions, and doubts that 1421 had already had.

The book consists of three parts. The first deals with the *Preparations* for fulfilling Emperor Xuande's mandate, especially the construction of a huge fleet and its characteristics; the types of gifts for foreign rulers; the significance for European navigation of the calculation of latitude and longitude by Zheng He's navigators; the determination of the position of the stars in the sky and the stellar tables for calculating longitude; and the previous voyage through the Red Sea to Cairo.

The second part: *China Ignites the Spark of the Renaissance*, focuses on the fleet's visit to Venice and Florence, along with the presence of such interesting figures as Niccolò Da Conti (c.1395-1469) and Paolo Toscanelli (1379-1482), and their relationship both with the Chinese ambassador (Zheng He), and with the maps used in their respective voyages by Christopher Columbus (1436-1506) in 1492 and Fernão de Magalhães (1480-1521) in 1519, so that both "discovered" what was already previously mapped; assesses and compares the world maps of Johannes Schöner (1477-1547) of 1515, Martin Waldseemüller (1470-1520) of 1507 and that of Admiral Zheng He of 1418, in relation to the knowledge of the world that China already had in 1434; compares the works of the mathematicians Toscanelli, Leon Battista Alberti (1404-1472), Nicholas of Cusa (1401-1464) and Johann Müller Regiomontano (1436-1476) in relation to the knowledge they had of Chinese mathematics through the Great Yongle Encyclopedia (Yongle Dadian) of 1421, composed of 11,095 books on all aspects of world knowledge: geography, cartography, agriculture, civil and military engineering, warfare techniques, health and medical care, construction and urban planning, steel and its production, ceramic firing and decoration, biochemistry and within it cross-fertilization, alcohol production, silk manufacture and weaving, gunpowder manufacture, shipbuilding, uniform codes, ciphers and cryptography; relates Leon Battista Alberti's work, "De Pictura", to the works of Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519) and of the latter to earlier Chinese inventions; compares Leonardo's drawings with the works of Francesco di Giorgio (1439-1502), Mariano di Jacopo known by the Taccola (1382-1453) and Alberti, in relation to the *Nung Shu*, a Chinese folk encyclopedia on agricultural machinery of 1313; discusses the presence of silk and rice in Italy from the Chinese imprint; the construction of large canals in Lombardy from the Chinese experience; the design and use of firearms and steel; the invention and development of the printing press from the beginning of the Ming dynasty (1051) and its later presence in Europe through Laurens Janszoon Coster (c. 1370- c.1440) in Harleem 1440, Johannes Gutenberg (c.1398-1468) in Mainz c.1440 and in Venice c.1441; synthesizes the contributions of China to the European Renaissance, the significance of world maps and their sphericity; the

³ See page 12 of the referred edition.

Croatian voyages led by Harvatye Mariakyr westward from secure cartography; the work of Johannes Kepler (1571-1630) and Galileo Galilei (1564-1642); the development of art and perspective; and the conversion of Europe into the center of world dominance.

The third part deals with *The Legacy of China*; where he details the great tragedy on the high seas due to the impact of the tsunami that destroys the fleet of Zheng He; he refers to the work of Cedric Bell in New Zealand where the impact of a comet opened the crater called Mahuika about 20 kilometers wide by 153 meters deep on the continental shelf of New Zealand at 48.3°S and 166°4'E, accompanied by a megatsunami; relates evidence of the existence of the tsunami in the shipwreck of a Chinese fleet in Oregon and British Columbia; in western Canada; along the west coast of the United States; refers to the Chinese settlements on the banks of the Columbia River and its confirmation by DNA; provides evidence of the shipwreck of Chinese fleets in South America; and concludes with a tour of Extremadura, in Spain, and the social situation of those who were later part of the conquerors in America.

In general, and after presenting in detail both his direct results and the contributions of very diverse authors, Menzies considers that:

The massive transfer of knowledge from China to Europe and the fact that it happened in a short period of time was the spark that ignited the revolution we call the "Renaissance".

Kings, captains, and navigators not only had for the first-time maps that showed them the true shape of the world, but they were also able to acquire instruments and charts that showed them how to reach those unknown lands by the quickest route and how to return home without getting lost.

When they arrived in the New World, a system of international trade created by the Chinese, Arabs, and Indians equivalent to half of the world's gross domestic product awaited them. The system in question was based on the exchange of Chinese manufactured goods for raw materials from the rest of the world. The trade model had been established through thousands of sea voyages over hundreds of years and had been perfected through centuries of monsoon and trade wind experience. When China disappeared from the world scene, Europe had no choice but to appropriate its trading system.⁴

The transmission of new scientific and technological knowledge for the time through dialogues, meetings, and printed texts, which took place in 1434, between an ancient civilization then open to cultural exchanges, which had been developing for thousands of years, and a Europe that was trying to overcome a millennium of stagnation following the fall of the Roman Empire. The Chinese seeds were sown in a very fertile soil. This is why the author states:

To this day the Renaissance has been described as a revival of the classical European civilizations of Greece and Rome. The influence of China has been ignored. In my view, while it is unquestionable that Greece and Rome played an important role, the transfer of intellectual knowledge from China was the trigger for the Renaissance.⁵

⁴ See pages 370-371 of the referred edition.

⁵ See page 292 of the present edition.

Again, the echoes of Eurocentrism against Menzies

As it happened with *1421*, this book has also had its detractors and for this reason the author, without referring to the matter, has relied on convincing proofs and on the results of other authors whose works have served him as a complement.

After the release of the book in the UK, Damian Thompson published in *The Telegraph* a very biased review of *1434*, where he tries to relate Menzies' work to recent developments in China in the context of the 2008 Olympic Games. Although, according to him, Menzies' work has been dismissed by other scholars as "drivel" Thompson wonders why so many are ready to accept Gavin Menzies' version of history. He estimates, "China PR is delighted with the triumph of the Beijing Olympics, and not remotely embarrassed by revelations of computer-assisted fireworks and other gimmicks. This is how Chinese brand management works and how it will work in the future."⁶ This he labels China's PR success story and links it to the launch of the book *1434* in UK bookstores.

However, for Thompson, *1434* "is not a history book in any meaningful sense of the term. This is because, to put it bluntly, a magnificent Chinese fleet did not sail to Italy in 1434, or, if it did, not a single witness recorded this incredible event. Did the Venetians have their backs to the water when they passed?" Everything indicates that the book was not read, since Menzies relies precisely on the work of Tai Peng Wang, the Canadian scholar of Chinese origin, who studied the Chinese and Italian chronicles that recorded the visits of Chinese delegations to Italy during the terms of the emperors Zhu Di and Xuande.

After considering, a priori, "that the Chinese circumnavigation of the world never happened", without assessing the dozens of evidences that appear in *1421* and those that are expanded in *1434*, he estimates that "Menzies is an exponent of disinformation disguised as a scholar with the help of footnotes, dubious quotations and confused logic" to allude to his book *Counterknowledge*, whose subtitle is: "How We Surrender to Conspiracy Theories, Quack Medicine, Fake Science and Fake History." In this way he refers that: "The growing spread of counterknowledge is a testimony to the greed and cowardice of the institutions (universities, large publishing houses, publicly funded broadcasting organizations) that used to insist that a fact was demonstrably true or plausible before disseminating it". All of the above is related to the Eurocentric fear of various research whose results, according to Thompson, "wish to supplant "the West" [through] interpretations of history and science".

This book by Menzies also serves as a pretext for Thompson to lambast China, particularly the international dissemination of Traditional Chinese Medicine and its healing properties, as an obvious act of counter-knowledge, for ignoring millennia of history and successful use. At the same time, he states: "As for Gavin Menzies' Sinophilic pseudo-history, the People's Republic can't get enough of it. Phoenix TV, a Murdoch-owned television company, has produced a documentary based on *1421* that has been played for audiences in China." Here again Thompson is unaware of or overlooks the dozens of documentaries that have surfaced on YouTube about Zheng He's travels in key languages worldwide such as Chinese, Spanish, English and French.⁷

Although he recognizes that: "Knowledge is power, and so is counter-knowledge, if you can propagate a variety that serves your purposes. In a world where we are free to choose 'facts' to suit

⁶ See Thompson, 2008.

⁷ See Guanhe., 2020:17-27.

our tastes or our commercial and political interests, history, like science, has become infinitely malleable." This also confirms the relativity of knowledge and its infinity, because when new knowledge appears, it is necessary to value the contributions of science and technology to the conscience and knowledge of new generations, and at the same time to free we from the straitjacket of obsolete cosmovision's considered valid at another time.

On the other hand, in the presentation of the book in Spain, Javier Gómez reviews in this regard:

Today we echo a controversial story, to say the least: the release in bookstores throughout Spain of Gavin Menzies' book entitled "1434", which raises the possibility (or certainty, according to its author) that Chinese knowledge was the origin of the Renaissance.

According to this writer/historian/mariner, in the year 1434 a Chinese fleet arrived in Tuscany on behalf of Emperor Zhu Di. According to the evidence he claims to provide, from Chinese and Portuguese records, they met with Pope Eugene IV in Florence, and there they brought their knowledge of astronomy, mathematics, architecture, steelmaking, and cartography.

It was all this knowledge that ended up being studied by great Italian figures and served as the basis for the future Renaissance. It was Paolo Toscanelli who acted as intermediary and sent a map to the Portuguese court that would later serve for the famous voyages of Columbus in which he would discover America. In this way, and according to his studies, the idea that it was Columbus who discovered the American lands would be disarmed, since in that map the American continent is perfectly visible, facts that he develops in his previous book, published seven years ago, "1421".

Since those years in which he published his first theses, Gavin Menzies has had to confront many historians who label his proposals as madness and who doubt the veracity of the data he provides. [...]

It is also curious, and for many, suspicious, that, if indeed the knowledge that reached Italy penetrated so deeply in Florence and developed the culture in Europe, why, if it was true, it did not also develop in China. [...]

Be that as it may, the scope that his theories are having, fruit of the controversy, will probably help him in the sales of his book, and at least me, as a follower of History that I am, and as long as the subject is not known in depth, for the moment, this theory remains as one more curiosity, as one of those theories that from time to time appear, and that, probably, it will be a long time before it is verified, if someday it comes to fruition.⁸

It is obvious that Javier Gomez either did not read the whole book, or he was carried away by the adverse opinion of several historians about the book *1421*. In the first place, it was not the Emperor Zhu Di, who suggested the trip to the West, since he had already passed away since 1424; but his grandson Emperor Xuande, a subject that is very well explained in the text. On the fact that Columbus was not the first to reach America there is already a very abundant bibliography on the subject and it is not only the results of *1421* and *1434*, respectively.⁹

When he states that "It is also curious, and for many, suspicious, that if indeed the knowledge that reached Italy permeated so deeply in Florence and developed the culture in Europe, why, if it was true, it did not also develop in China". Gomes does not consider that a very representative part of this knowledge was already systematized in *Yongle Dadian* (永乐大典). However, after Xuande's death, he was succeeded by his son Zhu Qizhen (1427-1464) when he was only eight years old, and it was the eunuch Wang Zhen who took charge of state affairs during his first years. Finally, Gomes sows doubt in the readers and motivates uncertainty.

⁸ See Gómez, 2009.

⁹ See, for example, Mann, 2006 and its sources.

Evidence vs. infundia

World map of 1418, centered on China and authenticated by its cartographic production in Quanzhou.

As can be observed, the referred critics do not speak of other complementary works that have served as sources to expand and corroborate approaches to the present work such as:

- Lam Yee Din, on the certainty of Zheng He's maps and travels.
- Tai Peng Wang, a Vancouver-based historian and journalist, on the authenticity of the 1418 map and its cartographic elaboration in Quanzhou, as well as the visits of Zheng He and his envoys to Cairo in 1414 and 1433.
- Cedric Bell, naval engineer, on some forty shipwrecks of Chinese junks in New Zealand, along with iron smelting huts and remains of furnaces for iron smelting.
- Rosanne Hawarden and Dave Bell, who continued Cedric Bell's work, on early Chinese settlers and other immigrants from Southeast Asia.
- Liu Gang, a lawyer, on the discovery in Shanghai of Zheng He's 1418 world map.
- Dave Cotner, former US Navy pilot, on the wreckage of an ancient Chinese ship off the coast of Oregon, USA, and the results of magnetic anomaly testing (MAS).

- Gunnar Thompson, expert on pre-Columbian remains in America, and his findings on the first Asian voyages between 1277 and 1287 sent by Kublai Khan (1215-1294).
- Siu-Leung Lee, expert in Chinese calligraphy, on the medallion found near Asheville (North Carolina) and its valuation as part of the gifts that Emperor Xuande sent to American tribal chiefs through his representative; as well as the consideration that during the Ming dynasty the Chinese reached as far as North Carolina.
- Paul Chiasson, a Canadian architect born on Cape Breton Island, on the oral traditions of the Mi'kmaq,¹⁰ local aborigines, about the arrival of foreigners from the other side of the world who settled on a cape now called Dauphin, whose study led to his book *Island of the Seven Cities* (Griffin, 2007),¹¹ with Buddhist ruins possibly predating the presence of Zheng He.
- Charlotte Harris Rees, on the first contacts of the Chinese in America. Her father, Dr. Hendon M. Harris, found an ancient Asian map showing the west coast of the American continent, which led him to write the 1975 book *The Asiatic Fathers of America: Chinese Discovery and Colonization of Ancient America* (Warwick House Publishing).¹² An abridged edition of this work was published by Charlotte in 2006.
- Robert Cribbs, associate professor of engineering at California State University and visiting professor of archaeology and scientific music in Cairo, Egypt, on the methods used by ancient and medieval astronomers to determine latitude and longitude, the ecliptic declination, the equations of time of the Sun and Moon, and the determination of longitude from the difference between sidereal and solar time or the angular distance between the Moon, astral, and stars.
- Benoit Larger and Albert Ronsin, from Saint-Dié-des-Vosges, France, on Martin Waldseemüller's maps of 1507 and 1516.
- Tan Ta Sen, Singapore businessman and President of the International Zheng He Society, on the verification and updating of data relating to Zheng He's travels between 1403 and 1434.

¹⁰ Also referred to as Micmac, L'nu and Mi'kmaw, they are an Aboriginal ethnic group of the Maritime Provinces of Canada and the Gaspé Peninsula of Quebec. They call this region Mi'kma'ki. Others live today in Newfoundland and northeastern Maine. The population is about 40,000, of which almost 11,000 speak Mi'kmaq, an Eastern Algonquian language. See "Mi'kmaq," in *Infogalactic*, <https://infogalactic.com/info/Mi%27kmaq>.

¹¹ In 2003, Chiasson explored the mountainous part of the island where he was born. Cape Breton is one of the oldest points of exploration in the Americas as it is littered with the remains of ancient settlements. Over the next two years, he surveyed the history of Europeans in North America and concluded that the ruins found did not belong to the Portuguese, French or English and predated the "discovery" of the island by John Cabot (Giovanni Caboto, c.1450-c.1499) in 1497. With aerial and site photographs, maps, drawings and his expertise in architectural history, the author gathers clues to one of the world's great mysteries. *The Island of the Seven Cities* reveals the existence of a large Chinese colony that thrived on Canadian shores long before the European Age of Discovery and reveals the first tangible proof that the Chinese were in the New World before Columbus. See https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/2087820.The_Island_of_Seven_Cities

¹² The work provides much evidence from both sides of the Pacific indicating the presence of Asia in U.S. territory at very early dates. It also indicates that at least occasional voyages back to Asia were made. The book explores some of the earliest Asian accounts of travel to a beautiful land to the east called Fu Sang. It explains how such travel was possible and included are photos of an ancient Asian world map showing the location of the legendary Fu Sang, right where the United States should be. See <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/6080959-the-asiatic-fathers-of-america>

- Lynda Nutter, dancer and choreographer, who knows Japanese, Chinese and Nyungah, the language of the aboriginal people living in the Swan Valley, east of Perth, Western Australia, on the discovery of carved stones that form an astronomical observatory from which longitude and latitude calculations can be made, together with the collation of inscriptions in medieval Chinese script in the middle of Nyungah territory to relate Zheng He's chart markings to the Perth coastline.
- Christopher Pollard, a scholar of medieval Spain, especially the history of Extremadura, on the presence of Extremadurians in the conquest of America.

Nevertheless, we must consider that Menzies treats in a bucolic way the characters that from Extremadura, except for Hernán Cortés (1485-1547), were expelled because of poverty, such as Vasco Núñez de Balboa (1475-1519), Francisco de Orellana (1511-1546), Francisco Pizarro (1478-1541), Hernando de Soto (1500-1542) and Pedro de Valdivia (1497-1553) until they became conquistadors and then mass murderers or accomplices in the murder of the native-american population. Undoubtedly this is due to the influence of the work of Christopher Pollard and his tourist enterprise in Extremadura, and the failure to consult other authors who have denounced the genocide of the conquest of America,¹³ a process that obviously began with the work of the Dominican Fray Bartolomé de las Casas (1474-1566).¹⁴

The critical reading of *1434. The year in which a Chinese fleet arrived in Italy and initiated the Renaissance*, is an occasion to verify the history, actuality, and validity of The Maritime Silk Road in the European context of the 15th century and its transcendence. This is linked to the origins of what today is the Chinese initiative of the *Belt and Road*, whose global scope is not new, but assumes greater dimensions in the light of the impetuous development of science and technology in the 21st century and is projected towards the common destiny of humanity in a context of necessary peace, greater socioeconomic harmony, social justice, and balance with the environment.

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¹³ See, among others, Mira and Guzmán. It is generally estimated that after the supposed "discovery" and conquest of America, the native population decreased radically, 95% of the total population of the continent died in the first 130 years after the arrival of Columbus.

¹⁴ See Las Casas, 1552.

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